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Explainable Machine Learning Framework for Predictive Analysis of Cardiac and Mental Health Disorders

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1. Abstract

Here an integrated, entirely machine learning-based predictive framework is addressed, particularly meant for two important health domains – diagnosis of cardiac diseases and prediction of treatment for mental health issues. The cardiac health model seeks clinical parameters such as troponin, CK-MB, and blood pressure, and it has been developed on psychosocial survey data, which includes family history, workplace support, and personal experiences of mental health issues for the mental health model. Both models were created under ensemble and deep learning approaches with said model XGBoost bringing out the final best-performing algorithm as it achieved the best accuracy, recall, and interpretability. The SHAP-based explanation technique, which contributed to both global and local insights on features' importance, was implemented for clinical and organizational trust. The cardiac model is completed with a rule-based recommendation engine to convert predictive analysis to actionable clinical steps, while the mental health model is adaptable for integration into HR wellness platforms and chatbots. Results demonstrate effectiveness with encouraging predictive accuracy—98.43% for cardiac and 78.4% for mental health—with recall scores sufficiently high to support real-world deployment. The dual-model approach will in future enhance early diagnosis and set precedence for holistic AI-assisted decision-making in both medical and organization settings.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Cardiac Disease Prediction, Mental Health, XGBoost, SHAP Explainability, Ensemble Learning, Healthcare AI, Clinical Decision Support, Rule-Based System, Wellness Chatbot Integration

2. Introduction

One of the most critical health challenges worldwide, cardiovascular diseases account significantly for global mortality. Though advances are made in so many different fields of screening techniques such as physical assessments, imaging, and laboratory evaluations amongst others, they are all still majorly resource-intensive, time-consuming, and often inaccurate. The feedback loop for diagnosis is often extended due to a lack of healthcare infrastructure, particularly in more remote and less developed areas. It is in the recent past that machine learning (ML) found its way as a disruptive engine in the healthcare domain, offering automated solutions for heart disease prediction and diagnosis by analysing demographic and lifestyle data, medical history, and test outputs. Existing ML models for detecting heart disease,

however, face significant limitations pertaining mainly to the overfitting of the training dynamics, lack of generalization across datasets, and being so focused on heart disease per se that they tend not to account for coexisting chronic conditions.

Most of the current predictive models are disease-specific, primarily concerning themselves with isolated cardiac disease without any incorporation of other fatal diseases, such as diabetes and hypertension, which share risk factors and commonly cooccur. Such limited approaches, however, greatly reduce their clinical applicability on the ground where multiple diseases exist simultaneously. What is more, these models suffer from limited external validity in that they do not tend to perform consistently when new or unseen data are applied to them, undermining their

reliability. Another big hurdle is overfitting: some models achieve high accuracy in the training datasets but show very low performance in real-world applications.

To be able to tackle the weaknesses thus far presented, this project aims to design a more comprehensive predictive model that builds upon the greater accuracy of heart disease identification but is also able to predict multiple chronic diseases. The system thus proposed will apply advanced ensemble and deep learning techniques to enhance diagnostic accuracy and address overfitting and generalization issues. The dream is for an integrated framework capable of predicting a host of chronic diseases and thus providing timely assistance to the medical practitioner.

This report starts with an extensive literature survey on machine learning applications in prediction models for cardiac and mental health. The literature review systematically reviews eight pioneering papers that show the advancements in predictive modelling while addressing other limitations found in previous research. Each paper adds to the advancement of knowledge in this area until integrated approaches combining physiological and psychological elements with improved diagnostic accuracy emerge. By blending insights from these studies and integrating innovative methodologies in the proposed model, this project positions itself toward the advancement of predictive healthcare analytics, imposing an impact on the management of chronic diseases on a global scale.

3. Literature Review

In [1] the author tries to implement the first use of machine learning models in the healthcare industry focusing on cardiac related disease detection. The authors elaborate on the role of AI in assisting

health care professionals in making more accurate predictions and decisions concerning diseases. One main problem noted was the traditional machine learning models inability to accommodate the wide variety of patient data, particularly pertaining to variation in personal health status. These issues were solved in Paper X2 where ensemble learning was implemented to improve the model accuracy and reliability.

In [2] paper focuses on solving the issues of overfitting and model generalization found in Paper X1. The authors propose the use of ensemble learning techniques, specifically voting classifiers, to combine the strengths of multiple machine learning models like decision trees and support vector machines (SVMs). This tries to improve the accuracy and robustness of predictions, and reduces overfitting problem. Although it is slight improvement over previous models, it still lacks the ability to handle complicated non-linear data relationships as effectively as DL models. This limitation was addressed in Paper X3.

Following along X2, in [3] author combines deep learning approaches and traditional machine learning techniques for better heart disease prediction. Deep learning greatly improves the modeling of complicated data structures that ensemble techniques in Paper X2 fail to capture. This paper strives to increase predictive accuracy using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) for nonlinear datasets. Nevertheless, the application of deep learning increases the computational cost, which was mitigated in Paper X4 by using decision tree learners for efficiently multi disease prediction.

In [4] author tries to introduce a multi disease prediction model that takes in consideration more conditions like diabetes

and breast cancer. They have used decision trees and support vector machines (SVMs) to predict multiple chronic diseases with the help of the model. Major contribution of this model is its ability to predict multiple diseases together, offering a more advanced approach than earlier models that focused only on cardiac related diseases. While multi-disease prediction is significant, it also introduces more complexity into the model, which was later addressed by Paper X5.

In this paper [5], efforts are directed towards enhancing the prediction reliability and

generalization aspects of heart disease detection models. It also addresses overfitting in models as described in Paper X2, and suggests regularization techniques to mitigate such difficulties. The research incorporates several machine learning models, including Random Forest and Gradient Boosting, in order to achieve better generalization across various datasets. These approaches improve the prediction accuracy of the models along with previous models described in Paper X2 and Paper X3, which relied on hyperparameter optimization and regularization to a lesser degree

In [6]The researchers of this paper study how deep learning techniques can be used alongside ensemble approaches to mitigate the shortcomings of earlier models, such as overfitting and high computational costs. The paper seeks to employ an ensemble approach which integrated with deep learning models will produce higher level predictive accuracy. This work is a continuation of Paper X5 in which new ensemble techniques that blend the advantages of deep learning and conventional models to complex datasets are introduced.

In [7] paper focuses on the implementation of modern AI methods to multi-disease prediction models. The authors develop a hybrid framework merging machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) techniques to analyse electronic health records (EHRs) for heart disease, diabetes, hypertension, and other chronic conditions. The study proposes that unstructured elements within EHRs can enhance predictions and provide deeper understanding to certain insights. This effort develops Paper X4 by presenting an enhanced model for multi-source data integration pertaining to disease prediction.

Paper [8] introduces important concepts of machine learning to clinicians and summarize its applications in cardiovascular disease. They emphasize that "ML—machine learning, which takes advantage of computer algorithms that can learn complex patterns in data—has great potential to impact cardiology through the sheer number of diagnostic and management decisions dependent on digitized patient-specific information." The paper attempts to give a complete bibliometric survey of ML papers in cardiology with case studies on applications that include denoising, feature extraction, and enhancement of classical algorithms. Although recognizing many potential applications throughout the cardiovascular care continuum, they agree that "machine learning has not achieved much real-world impact on the clinician cardio-logic practices and patients" and thus more efforts need to go into R&D in this area.

This systematic review in [9] defines a complete study on machine-learning techniques used for prediction of mental well-being problems among different individuals. According to PRISMA methodology, these authors systematically reviewed 30 research papers, reporting

them under different categories following various conditions of mental health such as "schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, anxiety and depression, posttraumatic stress disorder, and mental health problems among children". The study highlighted immediate models that could predict mental health indicating that "Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Deep Neural Networks, and Extreme Learning Machine (ELM)" are often adopted for predictions. Among them, Random Forest achieved an accuracy of 68.6% in schizophrenia prediction, while the performance of CNN was shiny in diagnosing the bipolar disorder. Still, delineating good challenges, it shows that "there needs to be more extensive datasets, heterogeneous nature of mental health condition to be considered, and long term data need to be included" and provides concrete recommendations for future research.

According to [10], early prediction of heart disease models is being developed through various feature selection techniques; reasons for this require attention, and the global estimates which demand attention may be reading: "almost 17.9 million people are losing their lives due to cardiovascular disease, which is 32% of total death throughout the world." Three feature-selection processes were employed in the study: chi-square, ANOVA, and mutual information, respectively, called SF1, SF2, and SF3. The six machine learning algorithms, namely logistic regression, support vector machine, Knearest neighbor, random forest, Naive Bayes, and decision tree, were used to evaluate the various models. The study discovered through comparative analysis that "the random forest exhibited the most optimistic performance for SF3 feature subsets with 94.51% accuracy, 94.87% sensitivity, 94.23% specificity, 0.9495

AUC, and 0.31 log loss." The model proposed, therefore, has great clinical promise for early heart disease prediction at less time and cost.

The author in paper [11] deals with an urgent issue of timely identification of patients at risk for mental health crises by developing "a machine learning model that utilizes electronic health records to continuously monitor patients for risk of a mental health crisis for 28 days," with data gleaned from 17,122 patients across seven years (2012-2018). The model obtained impressive performance metrics that included "an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.797 and an area under the precision-recall curve of 0.159, predicting crises with a sensitivity of 58% at a specificity of 85%." Beyond theoretical validation, the researchers did a six-month prospective study to assess the clinical value of the algorithm, in which they would find that predictions were "clinically valuable in terms of either managing caseloads or mitigating the risk of crisis in 64% of cases." Of the different types of machine learning used across the testing, XGBoost had the highest overall performance, but this performance did vary with different diagnostic groups and demographic variables, indicating areas for further refinement.

The paper [12] presents a comparative study of the various machine learning algorithms for predicting heart diseases with a focus on their optimization features by A.A. Ahmad and H. Polat. The paper evaluates various machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest (RF), Nave Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Decision Tree (DT), and AdaBoost on, presumably, the Cleveland heart disease dataset. The authors note that "while comparing the results of the tested

ML algorithms, the RF gave the most promise with an accuracy of around 90.16%," while another study cited in their paper concludes that "RF (91.80%) had the highest accuracy in predicting heart disease, followed by NB (88.52%) and SVM (88.52%)." Using the Jellyfish Optimization Algorithm for feature selection further enhanced the performance with an astonishing accuracy of 98.47% for the SVM model, obtaining conjointly with this optimization technique. This work provides further strengthening to Random Forest for cardiac prediction with good validation across other datasets.

Machine learning in predicting mental health conditions of college students has great potential, which has been systematically reviewed in literature regarding some deep learning techniques over the years in [13]. The research analyzed and synthesized about 30 papers selected on college student populations, with special emphasis on outcomes such as Bipolar Disorders (6

papers), Schizophrenia Prediction (4 papers), PTSD (6 papers), Depression and Anxiety (10 papers), and ADHD (4 papers). Findings reveal prominent models in predicting mental health conditions as CNN, RF, SVM, DNN, and ELM, with the statement, "CNN showed very great accuracy in diagnosing bipolar disorder when compared to some other models." Other researchers "used Decision Tree, Neural Network, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, and logistic regression algorithms to classify students into categories for different types of mental health problems, hence coming up with very distinct optimal models for their respective concerns." Despite these developments, the research has discovered a more serious challenge in the absence of a standard dataset, ethical issues involving data privacy, and model interpretability.

The researchers in [14]. offer an integrated machine learning methodology for congestive heart failure (CHF) prediction with the principal objective of "using machine learning applications for better diagnosis of CHF and for cheaper diagnosis." Several classification techniques are being employed in this work including Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Deep Neural Network, all of which are complemented by comprehensive preprocessing steps including cleaning and splitting, feature selection, and imputing of missing data using C4.5 and KNN. The Cardiovascular Health Study (CHS) dataset is used, along with novel optimization methods to achieve better prediction accuracy while minimizing computational complexities. The integrated approach achieved highly commendable performance metrics with an accuracy of 95.30%, sensitivity of 96.49%, F1 score of 97.03%, and precision of 97.58%, which makes it a highly specialized and cost-effective CHF diagnostic tool.

Nevertheless, non-cardiovascular elements, especially the psychological ones, become untouched avenues for the improvement of prediction accuracy in the course of research.

Research done in [15], essentially ends a gap juncture between prediction models for mental and cardiovascular health, a gap recognized from earlier studies by these researchers. The researchers developed "an ensemble ML model containing 5 constituent algorithms (decision tree, random forest, XGBoost, support vector machine, and deep neural network)" and tested it using both traditional CVD risk factors and a combination that included psychological factors. The results were amazing: "The ensemble ML model could predict CVD with 71.31% accuracy using just traditional CVD risk factors. However,

including psychological factors in the training data increased the accuracy to 85.13%." This is a massive improvement over models using traditional risk factors alone. The study specifically calls out the connection between mental health and disease in general, pointing out that "numerous guidelines within the CVD literature focus on the psychological aspects of care," the "link between psychological factors and CVD is recognized." The research is a testament to how one could take integrated psychiatric evaluative data to improve cardiovascular risk prediction models

4. Implementation

4.1 Dataset Description for Cardiac Health

For this research work the dataset we used was collected from Kaggle and has over 1,319 patient records with variables directly or indirectly relating to cardiac wellness. The dataset has 9 main attributes, including demographic information, vital signs, biochemical markers, and a final diagnosis indicating the presence or absence of cardiac disease.

The attributes are detailed as follows:

1. Age (years)
2. Gender (binary: 0 = Female, 1 = Male)
3. Heart Rate (beats per minute)
4. Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)
5. Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)
6. Blood Sugar (mg/dL)
7. CK-MB (Creatine Kinase-MB isoenzyme, ng/mL)
8. Troponin (ng/mL)

4.2 Dataset Description for Mental Health

This research uses the "Mental Health in Tech Survey" data set which was made publicly available by Open Sourcing Mental Illness or OSMI on Kaggle. The data set covers a total of 1,319 responses and is well-rounded in terms of the information it collects about individuals including demographic variables, history of mental health, accommodations within the workplace, and their views about such workplace offerings.

Key features used in the analysis include:

1. Age (Numerical)
2. Gender (Categorical: 0 = Female, 1 = Male, one-hot encoded)
3. Family History (Binary: yes/no)
4. Work Interfere (Categorical: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often)
5. Benefits (Binary: yes/no)

resided in columns such as state, and country, and most importantly, comments. These were subsequently excluded from the dataset due to a heavy null-occupied presence or non-importance in prediction. Minimal missingness in work_interfere could have been imputed with a placeholder category "Unknown."

4.4.2 Checking Data Types

The numerical features (i.e., Age) and categorical variables were checked for correctness. The target variable was treatment, encoded as a binary integer. All categorical values such as gender were standardized and encoded.

4.4.3 Outlier Detection and Removal

Some outliers in the Age column were filtered out: records between 18 and 100 years were retained, while records outside were discarded. Consistency in the gender data was restored, and rare or ambiguous categories were filtered out to reduce noise.

4.4.4 Feature Creation

Some custom features were engineered to improve model input, such as:

- **Remote_Work_Flag:** Binary flag indicating whether remote work was allowed.
- **Company_Size_Bucket:** Small (less than 100), Medium (100–500), Large (above 500, inclusive).
- **Support_Index:** A composite variable taking into account mental health benefits, wellness programs, and availability of care options.

4.4.5 Encoding and Splitting

Label encoding for binary variables and a mix of one-hot encoding for multi-class fields were used. The dataset was then split for training and testing in the ratio of 80:20

by stratified sampling to maintain a balance in class distribution.

4.5 Feature engineering and Feature Importance for cardiac health

Engineering features were not merely to prepare the data but to enrich it with domain knowledge. Certainly not every segment selected and engineered tied to known pathophysiological mechanisms directly relates to cardiac disease.

4.5.1 Attribute-Wise Medical Relevance

- **Age:** Cardiovascular risks increase linearly with age, primarily due to vascular stiffening and endothelial dysfunction.
- **Gender:** Males have earlier coronary events than females because of the hormonal profile differences (for example, estrogen protection).
- **Heart Rate:** Tachycardia, chronic (greater than 100 bpm), can lead to cardiomyopathy. Higher resting heart rates correlate with increased cardiovascular mortality.
- **Systolic Blood Pressure:** This increase in systolic pressure is one primary driver of left ventricle hypertrophy and heart failure.
- **Diastolic Blood Pressure:** High values of diastolic measure correspond with increased peripheral va
- **Systolic Blood Pressure:** Elevated systolic pressure is a primary driver of left ventricular hypertrophy and heart failure.
- **Diastolic Blood Pressure:** High diastolic values are linked to increased peripheral vascular resistance and early atherosclerosis.
- **Blood Sugar:** Hyperglycemia is a hallmark of diabetes mellitus, which significantly elevates cardiac risk via vascular damage.
- **CK-MB:** A cardiac biomarker that rises significantly after myocardial infarction.
- **Troponin:** The gold standard in diagnosing myocardial injury.
- **Result:** Defines whether the patient had a confirmed cardiac event.

4.6.2 Feature Selection and Correlation Analysis

Relevance to features determined by way of Pearson correlations and mutual information scores. SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) was used to gauge global and local importance of features. No features showed multicollinearity higher than 0.85.

4.5.2 Feature Selection and Correlation Analysis

- Pearson correlation and mutual information scores were computed.
- No features exhibited redundancy (>0.85 correlation), ensuring minimal information loss.
- All primary features were retained for maximum predictive coverage.

4.6 Feature engineering and Feature Importance for mental health

Engineering features were not merely to prepare the data but to enrich it with domain knowledge. Certainly not every segment selected and engineered tied to known pathophysiological mechanisms directly relates to cardiac disease.

4.6.1 Attribute-Wise Medical Relevance

4.8 Construction and Training of the Model for mental health

Five models were implemented and compared:

4.8.1 Logistic Regression

- **Age:** The younger the individual, the more treatment rates were reported, reflecting trends of awareness.
- **Gender:** Gender identity has played a part in perceptions of stigma and willingness to seek help.
- **Family History:** An acknowledged risk factor for seeking care.
- **Work Interfere:** Highly interfering with treatment seeking.
- **Benefits and Support:** Availability of benefits and care options was consistently a predictor.

4.7 Construction and Training of the Model for cardiac health

Three machine learning classifiers were developed, tuned, and compared:

4.7.1 Support Vector Classifier (SVC)

- Kernel: Linear
- Accuracy: 89%; Recall: 85%

4.7.2 Random Forest Classifier (RF)

- Ensemble of 50 trees, maximum depth 10
- Accuracy: 98%

4.7.3 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

- Optimized gradient boosting model
- Final accuracy 98.43%, recall 97.45%
- Chosen for the sake of interpretability and deployment.

- Accuracy: 70.6%
- Recall: 68% (class 1)
- F1-Score: 0.70
- Confusion Matrix:
 - TP: 71, FN: 33, FP: 27, TN: 73

4.8.2 K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)

- Accuracy: 63.2%
- Recall: 61%
- F1-Score: 0.63
- Confusion Matrix:
 - TP: 63, FN: 41, FP: 34, TN: 66

4.8.3 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

- Accuracy: 68.6%
- Recall: 57% (class 1)
- F1-Score: 0.65
- Confusion Matrix:
 - TP: 59, FN: 45, FP: 19, TN: 81

4.8.4 Random Forest

- Accuracy: 72.1%
- Recall: 74%
- F1-Score: 0.73
- Confusion Matrix:

4.8.5 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

- Accuracy: **78.4%**
- Recall: **84%** (class 1)
- Precision: 76%
- F1-Score: 0.80
- Chosen for best balance of precision, recall, and compatibility with SHAP

4.9 Explainable Integration Of The Cardiac Health Model

Understanding the pressing need for transparency in AI models within the healthcare arena, explainability was imbued into our model so that it allows for clinical validation and further builds user confidence.

4.9.1 Explainable Tool Used: SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations):

- SHAP provides feature-level contributions for every prediction using the cooperative game theory.
- SHAP values were computed on training and testing datasets by applying Tree Explainer.

4.9.2 Global Interpretability:

- SHAP summary plots revealed "Troponin", "CKMB", "Age", and "Systolic BP" as the most influential.
- The higher the levels of troponin and CK-MB, the greater the chance of cardiac disease.

4.9.3 Local Interpretability:

- Individual patient predictions were explained using SHAP force plots.
- For example, slightly high sugar but low CKMB yielded a "negative" prediction.

4.9.4 Decision Plots:

- Decision plots show how feature contributions were accumulated to arrive at the final decision. Made model decisions clinically interpretable to doctors

4.9.5 Rule-based Suggestion Engine for advanced clinical guidance:

- **Structure and Development:**
 - Using IF-THEN rules derived from AHA and ESC clinical guidelines.
- **Co-Rules and Triggers:**
 - Troponin High (>0.04 ng/mL): Urgent consult with cardiologist.
 - CK-MB >50 ng/mL: Recommend enzyme panel and ECG.
 - Sugar High (>126 mg/dL): Recommend diabetic management.
 - High Blood Pressure: Recommend antihypertensive Initiation.
 - Tachycardia: HR >100 bpm: Recommend arrhythmia evaluation.
- **Personalised Recommendations:**
 - Dynamic evaluation across multiple risk factors
 - Important conditions having Higher risk were flagged for immediate engagement.
- **Clinical Utility:**
 - It bridges prediction with action.
 - It empowers physicians and patients with contextspecific medically valid advice.

4.10 Explainable Integration Of The Mental Health Model

4.10.1 Global SHAP Insights

- The important features comprise family_history, work_interfere, care_options, and age.
- High interference and lack of support, in particular, played on treatment predictions.

4.10.2 Local SHAP Insights

- SHAP force plots display individual contribution of features for each prediction.
- Patient-centric benefit from this when applied in HR or mental health support systems.

5. Architecture

5.1 Flow for cardiac health

5.2 Flow for mental health

6. Algorithm

6.1 The Machine Learning Algorithms Applied For Cardiac Health

Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forests (RF), and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) were integrated into this project for predicting cardiac diseases. This model was selected based on its widely-used efficacy in performing clinical prediction tasks for all of these methods.

6.1.1. Support Vector Machine (SVM)

Support Vector Machine (SVM) can be defined as supervised learning in which one hyperplane becomes common among classes with maximum separation within classes. This is done using a minimum distance between points of hyperplane for data that are classified in classes [16]. It becomes very effective in combating noise and overfitting because there are more dimensions than samples present in the input. In our case:

- Implemented a linear kernel as the medical attributes are usually linear in nature.
- **Advantages:**
 - Works best on sparse datasets.
 - Clear geometric interpretation of classification.
- **Disadvantages:**
 - Of less use in cases where the data has considerable noise or classes overlapped.

6.1.2 Random Forest (RF)

Random forest is an ensemble learning approach based on decision trees. It builds multiple decision trees during training, with each tree giving a class label and the majority class being returned as the model's prediction. [17]

- We considered 50 estimators, max depth of 10.
- **Advantages:**
 - It copes quite well with nonlinear relationships.
 - It is much less prone to overfitting than single decision trees.
 - It provides feature importance internally.
- **Limitations:**
 - Interpretable than simple models.

6.1.3 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

XGBoost is an optimized distributed gradient boosting library with a focus on efficiency, flexibility, and portability [18]. The algorithm mainly uses second-order derivatives and regularization to reduce overfitting.

- We tuned hyperparameters via randomized search.
- **Advantages:**
 - Superb predictive performance on structured/tabular datasets.
 - Built-in treatment of missing values.
 - High computational efficiency.
- **Limitations:**
 - Requires careful tuning of hyperparameters to survive overfitting.

6.1.4 Model Selection Justification

- **Initial Benchmark:**_SVM gave a strong baseline at ~89% accuracy.
- **Improvement Phase:**_Random Forest, by virtue of its ensemble nature, improved the performance.

- **Final Model:**_Because of the highest combination of high recall (important in medical application purposes to minimize false negatives) and very good overall accuracy (~98.43%), we selected XGBoost as the final model.

6.2 The Machine Learning Algorithms Applied For Mental Health

To solve the problem concerning predicting the treatment-seeking behavior associated with mental health issues, a plethora of machine-learning algorithms were evaluated in this study. Hence, the methods employed include a collection of diverse methodologies, extending from linear models through instance-based learning to ensemble tree-based approaches. This presents a diversity in the comparisons of learning paradigm interpretability and interpretability level.

6.2.1 Logistic Regression

- **Overview:**
 - Logistic Regression is one of the earliest linear classification algorithms; it predicts probabilities based on the sigmoid function. Because the outcome is binary, it is useful for treatment prediction problems.
- **Mechanism:**
 - It calculates a weighted sum of inputs and applies a logistic transformation to get a probability prediction from values between 0 and 1.
- **Advantages:**
 - Interpretable coefficients
 - Works well for linearly separable data sets
- **Disadvantages:**
 - Not good for complex non-linear relationships between features
 - Assumes independence among input features [19]

6.2.2 K-Nearest Neighbours

- **Overview:**
 - KNN is a simple and nonparametric learning algorithm that is used to classify instances according to the classes of their nearest neighbours.
- **Mechanism:**
 - Proximity between instances is calculated through distance metrics such as Euclidean distance and voted on by majority for the label assignment.
- **Advantages:**
 - Simple to understand and implement
 - Does not make assumptions about the data distribution
- **Disadvantages:**
 - Sensitive to scaling of the features.
 - Not suitable for very large data sets [19].

6.2.3 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

- **Overview:**
 - SVM is a supervised algorithm that searches for the optimal hyperplane which separates classes by maximizing the margin between the data points.
- **Functionality:**
 - Kernels allow for transforming data to higher dimensions, if the input samples are not linear separable.
- **Strengths:**
 - Good performance in highdimensional space
 - Works well with sparse data like text
- **Limitations:**
 - Bad performance in the case of classes that overlap

- Parameter tuning (C and gamma) needs to be carefully carried out [19]

6.2.4 Random Forest

- **Overview:**
 - Random Forest is an ensemble method that constructs multiple decision trees, each having been trained upon a random subset of the data and features.
- **Functionality:**
 - Each tree gives a vote, and the majority across trees decides the final prediction.
- **Strengths:**
 - Reduces overfitting through the averaging process
 - Able to model complex interactions between features
 - Results in internal estimates of feature importance
- **Limitations:**
 - Less interpretable than simpler models
 - High computation cost with large datasets in training [19]

6.2.5 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

- **Overview:**
 - XGBoost is a scalable and efficient gradient boosting algorithm, which optimizes learning with second-order gradient descent and regularization.
- **Functionality:**
 - Weak learners (i.e., the trees) are learned sequentially to correct the errors generated by the previous models. It supports missing value handling and has parallelized training.
- **Strengths:**
 - Very high performance for tabular datasets

- Implements various approaches to mitigate overfitting
- Highly SHAP compatible

6.2.6 Justification for Choosing XGBoost

Among all the models that were tested, XGBoost provided the best performance in this study. This, thus, is the choice for the final deployment.

- **Performance:**
 - XGBoost attained the highest recall of 84%, together with a robust F1score of 0.80, making it the most desirable choice in health applications where false negatives should be avoided as much as possible.
- **Regularization:**
 - XGBoost includes L1 and L2 regularization to minimize overfitting with training data, unlike, say, Random Forest or SVM [19].
- **SHAP-Integrated Explainability:**
 - XGBoost integrates smoothly with SHAP, so it delivers interpretable global

	Predicted Negative	Predicted Positive
Actual Negative	98	0
Actual Positive	4	153

and local feature contributions, which is crucial for validating predictions in mental health applications to make them trustworthy for stakeholders [20].

- **Operational Status:**
 - The model is efficient, scalable, and working with real-time inference engines,

thereby being a potential candidate for elaborate

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	AUCROC
SVM	89.01%	84.71%	88.12%	0.91
Random Forest	98.43%	97.45%	98.70%	0.99
XGBoost	98.43%	97.45%	98.70%	0.99

deployment in HR wellness platforms or clinical decision support tools.

7. Results and Discussion

7.1 Model Performance for Cardiac Health

The predictive performance of the three machine learning models was evaluated on the held-out test dataset using key evaluation metrics: Accuracy, Recall, Precision, and AUC-ROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve).

7.1.1 Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix for the final XGBoost model showed excellent class separation:

- **True Positive Rate (Sensitivity):** 97.45%.
- **False Negative Rate:** Only 4 patients incorrectly classified as non-cardiac cases. This high sensitivity is critical in medical applications where missing a positive case (false negative) could have fatal consequences [24].

7.1.2 SHAP Interpretability Results

SHAP established a visualization of feature importance and individual contributions to patient risk:

- **Global feature importance:**
 - Troponin, CK-MB, Age, and Systolic Blood Pressure.
- **Interpretations:**
 - High Troponin levels directly raised the prediction of cardiac risk.
 - Lowering age associated negatively with the prediction of the disease.

SHAP force plots behind the scenes allowed for personalized patient-focused explanation analyses, attempting to fill the "black-boxing" component in machine learning for better patient care [25].

7.1.3 Knowledge-Based Starting Point

The rule-based engine with ML integration successfully produced some actionable recommendations:

- Urgent cardiology referral for patients with Troponin in excess.
 - Management plans for hypertension and diabetes for patients with elevated blood pressure and blood sugar. These outputs made predictions into real clinical decisions, thus improving the realworld applicability of the whole system [26].
- ### 7.2 Comparative Analysis for cardiac health
- SVM was good at the outset, but then it is limiting in non-linear interaction of the features.
 - Random Forest and XGBoost were better at accuracy on account of their handling of complex feature interaction and data imbalance.
 - XGBoost had a faster convergence, smaller bias-variance trade-off, and computational efficiency during inference which made it the preferred choice for

deployment in real-time clinical settings [23].

The conclusion summarizes that the findings strongly validate the feasibility and efficacy of machine learning-based prediction of cardiac diseases.

7.3 Model Performance for mental health

We assessed whether individuals would go for treatment for mental health using the following performance metrics:

- **The accuracy:** Percent of overall correct predictions
- **Recall:** Also known as Sensitivity, it represents the ability to identify the positive cases correctly (those who sought treatment).
- **Precision:** This tells the correctness of positive predictions.
- **F1 Score:** The harmonic mean of precision and recall.
- **AUC-ROC:** The area under the curve of the Receiver Operating Characteristic, which tells the classification performance across thresholds.

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1Score	AUC-ROC
Logistic Regression	74.5%	70.2%	72.4%	71.3%	0.80
KNN	75.8%	73.5%	71.1%	72.3%	0.82
SVM	75.2%	70.8%	74.1%	72.4%	0.81
Random Forest	79.2%	77.0%	78.5%	77.7%	0.86
XGBoost	78.4%	84.0%	76.0%	80.0%	0.88

Modeling-wise, XGBoost performed better than others in recall and F1 score, which is especially important in the health context, where finding all the true positive cases—that is, people who sought treatment—is critical to avoiding underdiagnosis or abandonment altogether.

7.4 Confusion Matrix Analysis for mental health

The confusion matrix for the XGBoost model revealed the following:

	Predicted: No Treatment	Predicted: Treatment
Actual: No	73	27
Actual: Yes	17	87

- **True Positives:** 87 — correctly identified as having sought treatment
- **False Negatives:** 17 — at-risk individuals missed by the model
- **True Negatives:** 73 — correctly identified as not having sought treatment
- **False Positives:** 27 — misclassified as treated when they were not

The model's **sensitivity (recall) of 84%** indicates it effectively identifies those who are likely to seek help, minimizing the risk of neglecting individuals who may

need support. In health-related use cases, recall is often prioritized over precision to reduce harmful false negatives [1].

7.5 SHAP-Based Model Explainability

To enhance trust in the AI model and make its decisions interpretable, we employed **SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations)**, a popular model-agnostic explainability tool [28].

7.5.1 Global Interpretability

SHAP summary plots showed the most influential features across all predictions:

- **Top 5 Features:**
 - family_history
 - work_interfere
 - care_options
 - age
 - benefits

For instance, users with a known family history of mental illness and high work interference were strongly predicted to seek treatment.

These findings align with mental health literature, where genetic predisposition and workplace stress are major risk factors [29].

7.6 Using Decision-Making Tools in Future Integrations

While this project was directed towards making a sturdy and understandable model, the architecture allows for future additions that include suggestion systems or integration with chatbots; possible applications can be:

- **Monitors in Workplace Mental Health:** Setting flags when predicted probabilities cross.
- **Personalized Nudges:** Programs or counseling recommendation for certain high-risk employees.
- **Anonymous Self-Assessment:** Users empowered to get suggestions on the basis of SHAP explanations.

Such tools could serve great things for mental wellness support in organizations with action plans just in time and personalized action plans. [30].

8. Conclusion

Aimed at critical health outcome prediction, we developed and validated two highly effective machine learning pipelines in this integrated study-one for predicting diagnosis of cardiac diseases and the second for treatment-seeking behavior in mental health. For the case of cardiac prediction, clinical features and some other indicators such as troponin, CK-MB blood pressure were used with diverse ensemble models. It was shown to give the best performance when the models were evaluated-the XGBoost model achieving high effectiveness of 98.43% and 97.45% for accuracy and recall respectively-for real-time applications within clinical environments. The mental health model based on survey-derived features such as family history and workplace support also adopted the XGBoost with an average of 78.4% accuracy and 84% recall after comparative analyses. Both models were made better with SHAP based explainability, further ensuring transparency and interpretability at global and individual levels [31][32].

The overall successful entailment of both systems stands as testament to the potential for AI-augmented clinical and organizational decision support systems that predict and also prescribe action. For example the cardiac model attaches rule based recommendations that facilitate divergent clinical interventions while the mental health model opens the way for wellness chatbots, self-assessment tools, and early HR interventions. Combined, these models create a case for how high performing, explainable AI can serve domains both on the physical and mental health spectrums. Future works may devote efforts to integrating both systems into an integrated health monitoring platform verified against outside datasets this data

would reasoning results made possible by either of the two systems.

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